

Synthesis, characterisation and biological studies of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes with drug lorazepam [7-chloro-5-(*o*-chlorophenyl)-1,3-dihydro-3-hydroxy-2*H*-1,4-benzodiazepine-2-one]

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Abstract : 1 : 1 complexes of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with drug lorazepam having general formula [ML(NO₃)₂.2H₂O] have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, IR and thermal studies. Analytical and IR data suggest that both complexes are monomeric due to coordination by N(1) and N(4) atoms. The ligand and complexes have been screened for their antimicrobial activities. Antimicrobial studies suggest that the Cu^{II} complex is more toxic than Zn^{II} complex.

Keywords : Lorazepam, copper(II) complexes, zinc(II) complexes.

Lorazepam a benzodiazepine is commonly used as a sedative drug particularly for relieving anxiety and insomnia¹. The survey of the literature² reveals that a little work has been done on the synthesis and physicochemical studies of transition metal complexes of lorazepam. Recent researches have established the detrimental effect of lorazepam, on both implicit and explicit memory and it is known to effect preceptual integration³. Lorazepam has two potential donor sites viz. the imine and azomethine group and hence it can form stable complexes with metal ions. On the basis of above reports, the present communication describes the synthesis, characterization and biological activity of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with drug lorazepam. The structure of ligand (drug) is

Lorazepam (LZ)

Results and discussion

Physical parameters of the ligand and the complexes are given in Table 1. Complexes are insoluble in organic solvents while moderately soluble in DMF and DMSO. The analytical data indicate 1 : 1 metal to ligand stoichiometry for both complexes. The coloured complexes are

stable at room temperature.

The molecular formulas of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes correspond to [(C₁₅H₁₀Cl₂N₂O₂)Zn(NO₃)₂.2H₂O] and [(C₁₅H₁₀Cl₂N₂O₂)Cu(NO₃)₂.2H₂O] having molecular weights 546.39 and 544.54. The ionisation and formation constants of ligand and divalent transition metal(II) complexes with lorazepam (drug) were calculated by measuring the magnitude of the proton displacement during the titration of ligand in absence and presence of metal ions against NaOH respectively. Ionisation and stability constants of ligand and Zn and Cu metal complexes are : 4.68, 9.96; 3.25, 8.15; and 2.42, 9.24 respectively.

In IR spectra of the Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} metal complexes the band attributed to the vibrational mode (C=O) appears at 1720 and 1718 cm⁻¹ showing small positive shift as compared to that of free ligand (1704 cm⁻¹). The band at 1628 cm⁻¹ of the free ligand is attributed to ν(C=N) while Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complex shows lowering of bands at 1607 and 1604 cm⁻¹ compared to the ligand, indicating the participation of azomethine N(4) nitrogen in complexation. The moderately strong band at 3365 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν(N-H) in the free ligand undergoes blue shift in Zn^{II} complex at 3325 cm⁻¹ and in Cu^{II} complexes at 3330 cm⁻¹ indicating the involvement of N(1) atom in coordination to the metal ion. In IR spectrum of the ligand the band at 3450 cm⁻¹ for ν(HC-OH), shows a small positive shift in Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. The IR spectra of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes show bands at 3560 and 3570

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the ligand and the complexes

Compd.	Colour and yield	Mol. Wt.	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found/(Calcd.)				
				C	H	N	Cl	Metal
Lorazepam (LZ)	White	321	160	55.98 (56.07)	3.08 (3.11)	8.79 (8.72)	22.06 (22.11)	-
ZnLZ(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Cream 77%	546.39	340	31.71 (32.94)	2.78 (2.56)	9.98 (10.24)	12.31 (12.99)	12.59 (11.96)
CuLZ(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Bluish green 68%	544.54	295	34.98 (33.05)	2.09 (2.57)	10.73 (10.28)	12.71 (13.03)	10.93 (11.66)

Table 2. Thermal decomposition scheme of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes

Decomposition scheme	Temp. range (°C)	Weigh loss (%) : Found/(Calcd.)
Zn(C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O ↓	51-98	7.09 (6.58)
Zn(C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂ ↓	98-378	27.41 (26.8)
Zn(C ₉ H ₆ N ₂ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂ ↓	506-585	23.44 (22.69)
ZnC ₃ + ZnO + other volatile oxides of C and N ↓	875	
ZnC ₃ + ZnO		
Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O ↓	47-122	6.79 (6.61)
Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂ ↓	122-297	16.36 (14.85)
Cu(C ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂)(NO ₃) ₂ ↓	502-712	24.02 (22.77)
Cu ₂ C ₂ + CuO + other volatile oxides ↓	884	
Cu ₂ C ₂ + CuO		

Table 3. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of the ligand (LZ), metal nitrates and its complexes

Compd.	Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity			
	Zone of inhibition (in mm)				Zone of inhibition (in mm)			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. flavous</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. triticena</i>	<i>F. species</i>
Lorazepam (LZ)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Zn(NO ₃) ₂	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CuLZ(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	42	35	35	42	40	40	40	40
ZnLZ(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	40	40	40	40	36	36	42	36
Standard drug	30	35	35	35	30	30	30	35
Control DMF	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

cm^{-1} respectively may be due to νOH of water molecule. The bands in the IR spectra of Zn^{II} complex at 485 and 346 cm^{-1} and in Cu^{II} complex at 517 and 470 cm^{-1} are due to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ linkage⁴. Other strong bands at 1362 and 882 cm^{-1} in Zn^{II} complex and 1383 and 861 cm^{-1} in Cu^{II} complex suggest the monodentate nature of νNO_3 ⁴.

The thermal decomposition scheme of complexes are given in Table 2.

The biological activities of Zn^{II} complexes, metal nitrates and ligand were screened against fungi *A. flavous*, *A. niger*, *P. triticena* and *F. species* and bacteria *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*. The zone of inhibition of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of fungal and bacterial species are given in Table 3.

The above data indicate that the zone of inhibition at 500 ppm concentration of the complexes is the best. The result shows that the Zn^{II} complex is more effective against fungi *P. triticena* while Cu^{II} complex is more effective against bacteria *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. It also shows that the Cu^{II} complex of lorazepam is more effective as compare to Zn^{II} complex and drug lorazepam it self.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analar grade and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The complexes were prepared by mixing the molar solutions of $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (dissolved in double distilled water) and ligand lorazepam (dissolved in ethanol), in (1 : 1) ratio. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted between 8 to 9.

The stoichiometry of the complexes was found by carrying out potentiometric titration of ligand and metal solution in (1 : 1) ratio against standard NaOH (0.1 M) solution in ethanol-water mixture. The pH changes observed during the titration were plotted against moles or alkali (m) added per moles of metal ion and ligand. The stoichiometric ratio was confirmed by Fenger's method⁵.

The purity of complexes were confirmed by TLC carried out on silica gel-G plate using ethanol : benzene (80 : 20) mixture.

The complexes were analysed for metal and chlorine content by standard procedure. Thermogravimetric analysis up to $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer. Thermal analysis systems in static air with heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. IR spectra of ligand and its metal complexes were recorded in (KBr) matrix on Perkin-Elmer 842- spectrophotometer. Elemental analysis of C, H, N were carried out at NCL, Pune.

Antimicrobial activity of drug lorazepam and its metal complexes have been done by Broth serial Dilution Method⁶. The results are presented in Table 3.

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References

1. C. Salzman, "Task Force on Benzodiazepine Dependency". American Psychiatric Association, Washington, DC, 1990; For A General review about Benzodiazepines Sec. Burgers Medical Chemistry and Drug Discovery : *Therapeutical Agent*, 1997, 2, 5.
2. A. Mosset, J. P. Tuchageus, J. J. Bonnet and R. Haran, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 290; M. Cusumano, A. Gianetto, P. Ficcara, R. Ficcara and S. Tomassini, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1991, 1581; V. Vinkovic, Z. Raza and Sunjic, *Spectros. Lett.*, 1994, 27, 269.
3. T. Beckers, J. Way Cmans, M. Boucant and A. Glersch, *Vision Research*, 2001, 41, 17.
4. K. Nakamoto, J. Fujita and H. Murata, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 4817; N. F. Curtis and Y. M. Curtis, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 804.
5. P. Job, *Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1928, 9, 113.
6. J. H. Quasted, *J. Gen. Microbiol.*, 1966, 45, 14.